

Reuse of Public Keys Across UTXO and Account-Based Cryptocurrencies

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Abstract. It is well known that reusing cryptocurrency addresses undermines privacy. This also applies if the same addresses are used in different cryptocurrencies. Nevertheless, cross-chain address reuse appears to be a recurring phenomenon, especially in EVM-based designs. Previous works performed either direct address matching, or basic format conversion, to identify such cases. However, seemingly incompatible address formats e.g., in Bitcoin and Ethereum, can also be derived from the same public keys, since they rely on the same cryptographic primitives. In this paper, we therefore focus on the underlying public keys to discover reuse within, as well as across, different cryptocurrency networks, enabling us to also match incompatible address formats. Specifically, we analyze key reuse across Bitcoin, Ethereum, Litecoin, Dogecoin, Zcash and Tron. Our results reveal that cryptographic keys are extensively and actively reused across these networks, negatively impacting both privacy and security of their users. We are hence the first to expose and quantify cross-chain key reuse between UTXO and account-based cryptocurrencies. Moreover, we devise novel clustering methods across these different cryptocurrency networks that do not rely on heuristics and instead link entities by their knowledge of the underlying secret key.

1 Introduction

It is well known that reusing cryptocurrency addresses, both within the same cryptocurrency, as well as across different networks (cross-chain), undermines the privacy of users and impacts security [Mei+13; HSI18; Lin+25]. In this paper we explore a simple, yet powerful, technique to cluster entities within and across different cryptocurrencies by focusing on the underlying cryptographic keys used for signing transactions, rather than the addresses which are derived from these keys. Hereby, we leverage the fact that many cryptocurrencies rely on the same

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^{**} A full version of this paper with extended network metrics and methodological descriptions is available in [Stü+26].

underlying cryptographic primitive, namely ECDSA over *secp256k1*⁵, for signing in a majority of transactions.

Previous research has focused either on direct address matching or conversion between compatible address formats to link key reuse within and across closely related UTXO cryptocurrencies [HSI18; Kal+20; SY25] and, independently, within EVM-compatible account models [Zha+22; Lin+25]. However, by relying on addresses rather than directly on the underlying public keys, these analyses are limited to cryptocurrencies with compatible address/hash types. Crucially, the address formats of the most prevalent designs for UTXO and account based systems, i.e. Bitcoin and Ethereum, are not compatible although both use the same digital signature scheme and curve for most transactions. Hence, until now key reuse⁶ across these two different designs has not been explored.

Fig. 1. Address formats of different cryptocurrencies can be derived from the same public key. Some formats may be converted into each other without knowledge of the underlying public key while others can not.

In this work we address this research gap by treating the public keys associated with different cryptocurrency addresses as first-class citizens in the context of key reuse. Knowledge of a public key allows us to generate a one-to-many mapping (from public key to addresses) both within, as well as across different cryptocurrency designs (see Figure 1 for details⁷). Since any *active* use of crypto-assets generally requires a matching digital signature, the underlying public key is necessarily revealed. This implies that the *same* cryptographic keying material, potentially used in *different* cryptocurrencies, can be linked to the same entity controlling the respective key.

We analyzed six different cryptocurrencies: Bitcoin (BTC), Ethereum (ETH), Litecoin (LTC), Dogecoin (DOGE), Zcash (ZEC) and Tron (TRX) and found

⁵ <https://www.secg.org/sec2-v2.pdf>

⁶ For the most part address reuse also implies reuse of the same cryptographic keys.

⁷ To simplify the illustration the *compressed* public key is not included in Figure 1.

that a total number of 1,604,614 keys have been reused in at least two of the considered systems. Our results reveal that key reuse across cryptocurrencies appears to happen at a considerable scale. Hereby, focusing on public key reuse allows us not only to link entities across cryptocurrencies with inconvertible address formats, but also to potentially link UTXO style transactions with only one input. Moreover, in combination with other (existing) clustering techniques, such as multiple-input heuristics, our cross-cryptocurrency key reuse clustering method can also be used to cluster account based designs such as Ethereum. Summarizing, we make the following contributions:

- We show that cryptographic keys are extensively and continually reused across all of the analyzed blockchain networks, with 1,604,614 reused keys, thereof at least 1,429,008 keys have been *actively* reused.
- We present the first cross-chain key reuse analysis between UTXO and account models and show that a significant number of public keys are reused, namely 497,178 between Bitcoin and Ethereum and 831,056 in total between all of the analyzed UTXO and account models, accounting for roughly 50% of all observed reused keys.
- We show that it is possible to cluster addresses associated with reused keys in account based cryptocurrencies based on their clustering in an UTXO cryptocurrency.
- To validate our approach, we reproduce the findings from related work that relies on address-based key-reuse detection [SY25; HSI18], as well as leveraging similarities between Ethereum and Tron. Hereby, our key-based methodology can lead to further improvement by identifying reuse cases where direct address conversion between formats is not possible.

2 Background

Addresses are a core abstraction in cryptocurrency systems. They act as pseudonymous identifiers that bind public keys of digital signature schemes to assets and thereby support publicly verifiable authorization of spends. Reuse of an address (or its underlying key) weakens unlinkability and enables entity inferences at scale, a phenomenon extensively leveraged in prior work on tracing and clustering [RH12; Mei+13]. In UTXO-based designs, the *multiple-input heuristic* was the first widely-used clustering technique: inputs co-spent in a transaction are likely controlled by the same entity [RH12; Mei+13]. While effective, it is i) inapplicable to single-input models and ii) susceptible to intentional obfuscation (e.g., Coin-Join/PayJoin) [Gla+22; Ghe+21]. The account model lacks a direct analogue to multiple-input heuristics. To overcome this limitation Victor et al. [Vic20] present Ethereum-specific heuristics that exploit on-chain behavior, notably exchange deposit address reuse, airdrop multi-participation, and token transfer self-authorization, clustering a substantial fraction of active EOAs (Externally Owned Accounts).

Depending on the system design, the *same* public key may be associated with different addresses within the same cryptocurrency, e.g. by using different script

types in Bitcoin-like UTXO models⁸. While Kalodner et al. [Kal+20] already briefly mention this form of *internal* key reuse⁹, its potential relevance, e.g in the context of clustering heuristics, is not discussed. In recent concurrent work, Smolenkova et al. address this issue and present a *single chain* address grouping method called *KeyLinker*, that leverages convertible address formats to identify internal key reuse in Bitcoin [SY25]. A crucial difference to our work however, aside from the single cryptocurrency setting, is that the presented method relies on address conversion for reuse detection. Their approach is therefore limited to convertible address formats and can not detect key reuse in the case of incompatible address representations, such as those derived from compressed and uncompressed public keys.

Cross-chain mechanisms (bridges, atomic swaps, messaging protocols) underpin asset mobility across heterogeneous ledgers [Zam+21], and prior cross-ledger studies target *transaction* association or *entity* resolution via address-relationship heuristics and on-chain semantics [YKM19; Zha+22; Lin+25].

Closer to our focus on cross-chain *public key reuse*, Harrigan et al. (HSI) demonstrate that an airdrop in CLAM, which reused address encodings from other UTXO chains, enables *cross-chain address clustering* across BTC, LTC and DOGE and can reveal ownership on one chain through activity on another [HSI18]. BlockSci also provides a *Multi-chain* mode for Bitcoin-like UTXO models that allows for address based cross-chain clustering similar to HSI. The paper also analyzes key-reuse between Bitcoin and the *Bitcoin Cash* hard fork [Kal+20]. In [HH19] the impact of hard forks on cross-chain traceability in Monero is analyzed by leveraging the reuse of mixins across forks. Public keys have also been analyzed across chains to expose biased ECDSA nonces [BH19], deanonymization risks at Ethereum’s P2P layer [Li+25], and cross-chain identity correlation [COM22].

These previous lines of work motivate and contextualize our approach: while prior efforts either presume identical address formats (EVM) or leverage shared or convertible encodings among UTXO-like systems [HSI18; Kal+20; SY25], we exploit *cross-chain public-key reuse* to bridge the heterogeneous designs of the UTXO *and* account model, thereby expanding the space of cross-chain/entity linkage beyond address-string equality.

3 Dataset and methods

Most cryptocurrency protocols do not explicitly disclose a recipient’s public key within a transaction; instead, they utilize an encoded hash of the key, known as an *address* [Bon+15]. The underlying public key remains hidden until the funds are subsequently spent, at which point the spending transaction must provide a digital signature that reveals the key for network validation.

We gathered transaction data from six representative cryptocurrencies (BTC, LTC, DOGE, ZEC, ETH, and TRX) ending with the blocks mined just prior to

⁸ See [Stü+26, Appendix C] for a listing of different Bitcoin script types.

⁹ In *BlockSci* such addresses are referred to as *equivalent*, see https://citp.github.io/BlockSci/reference/addresses/equiv_address.html

April 1, 2025 (cf. [Stü+26, Appendix A]). Note that neither of the considered systems share a common transaction history, i.e. are permanent forks [Zam+18], which could skew our analysis of key reuse. These transactions have been used to extract *secp256k1* public keys. Since retrieving public key information is not immediately possible through common APIs, the extraction procedure had to be adapted depending on the cryptocurrency as well as the respective transaction type. It is generally¹⁰ not possible to extract the public key directly from addresses without a spending transaction, due to the preimage resistance properties of the underlying cryptographic hash function [KL20] predominantly used in address generation. Passive usage patterns where funds are only ever received at an address is also the reason why we distinguish between two different classes of key reuse.

3.1 Classification of Key Reuse

For our analysis, we differentiate between *active-* and *passive key reuse* (see Definition 1). Active key reuse indicates the usage of the same secret key for signing (i.e., sending) a transaction in more than one cryptocurrency, while passive key reuse indicates that the same address has been used on the receiving side of a transaction in more than one cryptocurrency.

Definition 1. [*Cross-chain Key Reuse*] *If asymmetric key pairs are used in more than one cryptocurrency in at least one transaction each, either on the sending or receiving side, we call this a (cross-chain) key reuse event, or a reused key respectively. We further differentiate between:*

- **active key reuse:** *When the keying material is actively used to sign e.g., a transaction, in at least two cryptocurrencies, we call it an active key reuse.*
- **passive key reuse:** *When the keying material is actively used for signing in at most one cryptocurrency and for all other cryptocurrencies the key is only passively involved on the receiving side, we call it a passive key reuse.*

We introduce this separation since passive key reuse is not preventable by the owner of the respective key. Specifically, once the public key has been disclosed anywhere or the associated address(es) can otherwise be inferred, transactions that are directed towards these addresses can generally not be prevented. Active reuse, on the other hand, requires knowledge of the respective private key. Therefore, it is a strong indicator that the same entity is involved in those transactions¹¹. In the six cryptocurrencies that we analyzed, 1,604,614 keys have been reused in at least two of them, thereof 1,429,008 keys have been *actively* reused in more than one cryptocurrency.

¹⁰ Exceptions such as Bitcoin *Pay to Public Key (P2PK)* or *Pay to Multisig (P2MS)* transactions can exist.

¹¹ Exceptions to this rule would be key loss/compromise or the use of threshold ECDSA [LN18; Won+23], which would allow multiple potential signers to produce a single signature. At the time of writing this is however not widely used.

3.2 Data Extraction

Our proposed analysis technique for key reuse requires that the respective public keys have been revealed at least once. However, most cryptocurrency transaction types do not immediately disclose the public key of a recipient directly. The only exception to this rule in our dataset are *Pay to Public Key* (P2PK¹²) and *Bare Multisig* (P2MS¹³) transactions in Bitcoin and Litecoin, respectively. The use of P2PK is predominantly documented in the coinbase transactions of the blockchains’ initial blocks. The P2MS script type is a historical artifact within the Bitcoin protocol, rendered largely obsolete by the introduction of *Pay to Scripthash* (P2SH) in 2012. Both transaction types have long been deprecated and account for only a small number of transactions (e.g. for Bitcoin 1,271,869 P2PK (0.11%) and 1,434,621 P2MS (0.12%) transactions, respectively). Therefore, almost all public keys we collected for our analysis have been actively used on the sending side at least once.

UTXO Cryptocurrencies A modified version of *bitcoin-etl*¹⁴ was used to extract and store transaction data for all considered UTXO cryptocurrencies in JSON format. This modified version included additional fields to capture Segregated Witness (SegWit) data, which is essential for a comprehensive analysis of UTXO-based cryptocurrencies. UTXO outputs can be created with different types of locking scripts, which define the conditions under which those specific coins can be spent in the future (see [Stü+26, Appendix C] for further details). Over time, UTXO output types have evolved to improve efficiency, privacy, and functionality [JP23]. While these scripts often correspond to standard addresses (e.g., P2PKH or P2WPKH), they can also represent more complex conditions such as multisignature requirements or time locks. A single transaction might create outputs with different spending conditions for various purposes.

To extract the ECDSA public keys associated with a respective address, we had to adapt the extraction to the particular transaction type (cf. [Stü+26, Appendix C.1]). Table 1 shows the total counts of extracted unique public keys, split into the respective output types.

Currency	P2PK	P2MS	P2PKH	P2SH	P2WPKH	P2WSH	Total count
BTC	217,060	3,543,439	580,334,145	517,671,478	302,098,052	59,772,637	1,462,721,776
LTC	300,688	34	65,420,695	164,912,000	121,245,406	1,144,188	352,973,720
DOGE			82,459,658	1,873,438			84,332,852
ZEC			7,434,678	1,125,355			8,560,024

Table 1. Number of UTXO transaction types and total counts of extracted unique public keys.

¹² <https://learnmeabitcoin.com/technical/script/p2pk>

¹³ <https://learnmeabitcoin.com/technical/script/p2ms>

¹⁴ <https://github.com/blockchain-etl/bitcoin-etl> (version 1.5.2)

Account Based Cryptocurrencies For our analysis we parsed all Ethereum transactions initiated by EOAs and extracted a total of 226,017,011 unique public keys using the public key recovery method described in [Stü+26, Appendix D]. This was necessary because the Ethereum node that was used to query blockchain data (Geth¹⁵) does not provide a way for retrieving the public key directly. The code we developed for this recovery is provided on GitHub¹⁶. Due to the large number of Tron transactions (cf. [Stü+26, Appendix A]), we did not perform signature recovery for every transaction and instead first identified the relevant subset of 266,333,226 transactions where a new source/owner address (i.e. EOA) first performed a transaction before recovering the unique associated public keys. Furthermore, we restrict our extraction of public keys in ETH and TRX to EOAs and leave other scenarios, such as signature verification in smart contract executions, to future work.

3.3 Validation of our Approach

To validate our approach of identifying cross-chain key reuse through the underlying public keys, we compare our results with: i) The results presented in HSI [HSI18] on address reuse in Bitcoin, Litecoin and Dogecoin ii) A ground truth between Ethereum and Tron which we are able to obtain due to their mostly compatible address format and iii) *Internal*, i.e., single chain key-reuse in Bitcoin with the results in [SY25], which we discuss in Subsection 4.2.

The approach in HSI relies on the fact that all of their considered systems use address formats that encode a hash digest of the respective public key or Bitcoin-compatible spend script derived by the same hash function. Therefore, these hashes are used for comparison (not the entire address). The advantage of this approach: It can also identify reuse of addresses (and thus keys) which are used *exclusively passive*. The disadvantage is that this technique only works across cryptocurrencies with the same underlying address hash formats.

By computing our public key based analysis for the block range in HSI we are able to compare our approach against their results¹⁷. As expected, when relying only on public keys the instances where *exclusively passive* cross-chain reuse occurs cannot be identified. We identified 59% of the HSI reuse cases for Bitcoin-Litecoin, 89% cases for Doge-Bitcoin, and 93% for Doge-Litecoin. Surprisingly, when comparing our methodology to HSI's up to our current block range the public key based approach exceeds expectations: Reaching from 89% for Bitcoin-Litecoin to 200% for Bitcoin-Doge and 300% for Litecoin-Doge. Possible explanations are that HSI's method does not work between P2WSH (SHA256) and P2SH (RIPEMD160), as well as compressed and uncompressed keys. Moreover, Doge makes extensive use of P2SH, for which address based reuse checks are less effective compared to public key extraction, e.g., in case of multi-sig transactions.

For validating our approach in account based systems, we rely on the fact that Ethereum and Tron share the same underlying Ethereum address format, where

¹⁵ <https://geth.ethereum.org>

¹⁶ <https://gist.github.com/kernoelpanic/423c61f90e81e4c9d473ff6fda783559>

¹⁷ See [Stü+26, Appendix E.1] for details.

Tron just encodes a prefixed version of the Ethereum address with Base58¹⁸. Decoding Tron addresses to bring them into the same format allows us to obtain a ground truth which also captures addresses which are used *exclusively passive*. Compared to this ground truth, we were able to identify 91% of reuse events based on our method of public key extraction, which is in line with our previous comparisons, suggesting that around 90% of cross-chain key reuse can be identified when exclusively relying on public keys. This provides a strong indicator for the validity of the approach also in instances where no ground truth is available and address formats are not readily convertible, as in the case of reuse between UTXO and account based systems.

4 Analysis & Results

4.1 Active Public Key Reuse across Different Blockchain Networks

Building on the extracted dataset, we analyze active cross-chain public key reuse. By treating keys from each cryptocurrency as discrete sets, we identify cross-network reuse through set intersections. We visualize these intersections using an UpSet plot, which offers superior scalability over traditional Venn diagrams for multi-set comparisons. The plot uses bar charts to denote cardinality and a matrix layout to indicate specific set memberships; Figure 2 highlights the Top 5 cardinalities for each intersection size. For a complete representation of all identified intersections we refer to [Stü+26, Appendix F].

We identified a total of 1,604,614 reused keys, of which at least 1,429,008 were actively used for sending transactions across more than one cryptocurrency, indicating a deliberate action by the key holder.

Fig. 2. Cardinality of set intersections for active public key reuse across the considered currencies (Top 5 cardinalities per intersections size).

¹⁸ See [Stü+26, Appendix E.2] for details.

4.2 Temporal Analysis

Whether public key reuse is a phenomenon of the past or present is a key question. While early Bitcoin users might have reused keys due to a lack of privacy awareness and immature wallet software, it is unclear if this behavior has persisted. Given that UTXO-based cryptocurrencies permit multiple address formats to be derived from a single key, our analysis proceeded in two stages: First, we examined key reuse within single UTXO chains. Second, we conducted a longitudinal investigation into public key reuse across distinct blockchain networks.

UTXO Internal Active Reuse Figure 3 shows the quarterly counts of UTXO internal reuse events for Bitcoin and Litecoin, revealing that internal public key reuse on these networks remains a current phenomenon. Hereby, our results confirm the findings in [SY25] that relies on convertible address formats to detect internal key-reuse in Bitcoin. We further show that while internal reuse can also be observed in other UTXO cryptocurrencies, e.g. Litecoin, the occurrences may be very low (Zcash). The ordering of the address formats highlights which format was first used for a public key. A significant concentration of UTXO internal active reuse events is observed within two specific public key type pairs: The pair P2PKH-P2WPKH accounts for the largest proportion at 44.6%, while the converse order P2WPKH-P2PKH follows with 32.9%. Combined, these two pairs represent approximately 77.5% of the total internal reuse events, indicating their dominant role in the observed reuse patterns. The remaining public key type pairs account for the residual proportion of 22.5%.

Note that P2PKH-P2PKH internal reuse (1.8%) refers to instances where one address was derived from the uncompressed format of the public key and the other from the compressed format. This occurs in either order, meaning the first transaction could use an address from an uncompressed key and the subsequent transaction an address from a compressed key, or vice versa.

The internal reuse analysis of Zcash revealed a total of four instances of internal public key reuse. Conversely, in Dogecoin a median of two first active internal key reuse events were documented per quarter, peaking at 168 events within the first quarter of 2018.

Fig. 3. Quarterly counts of first UTXO internal active public key reuse events within Bitcoin (BTC) and Litecoin (LTC).

Cross-chain Active Reuse The cross-chain reuse of public keys over-time is shown in Figure 4. Again, the order of the cryptocurrency tickers indicates in which cryptocurrency the underlying public key was used first. The six most frequent currency pairs involve the three dominant cryptocurrencies BTC, ETH, and TRX. Their reuse events constitute approximately 73.3% of all observed first active cross-chain reuse events, highlighting their central role in the observed transactions. Notably, the TRX-ETH pair accounts for the largest proportion of these events, at 23.3%. Here, we observe that it is more common that public keys are first used in TRX before they are used in ETH, than the other way round. The remaining currency pairs not listed (category *Other* in Figure 4) collectively represent the remaining 26.7% of reuse events, indicating a significant concentration of activity within the six most frequent pairs.

Fig. 4. Quarterly counts of first active public cross-chain reuse events.

4.3 Improve any Clustering through Reused Keys

Since the (re)use of the same cryptographic key necessitates control over the associated private key, this is a strong indicator that the same entity is behind all derived cryptocurrency address formats across the respective chains. This rationale can be used to improve any existing clustering method by merging clusters with different addresses derived from the same underlying public key.

Depending on the cryptocurrency design, it may be possible to associate public keys with more than one address, in which case this rationale can also be applied to a *single* cryptocurrency¹⁹. In concurrent work Smolenkova and Yanovic introduce and discuss such a single chain address clustering method in the context of Bitcoin [SY25]. Their methodology, however, relies on convertible address formats rather than extraction of the underlying public keys.

The primary goal of our work is to analyze and quantify *cross-chain* key reuse, whereby address formats may not be directly convertible and hence extraction and reliance on the underlying public keys is necessary. By first applying our key-based approach to the single chain setting, we are not only able to verify the results from [SY25], but can also provide a lower bound on the internal key reuse

¹⁹ The basic process on the example of Bitcoin is shown in [Stü+26, Appendix G].

events that cannot be captured by address conversions. Interestingly, we find that for internal key reuse across the analyzed UTXO designs the reuse between compressed and uncompressed public key formats only accounts for 1.8% of all observed key-reuse events and 1.99% in the case of Bitcoin only.

Our analysis method starts with the initial clustering derived from the multi-input heuristic. In a second step, we merge all clusters (i.e., recompute the connected components) which contain addresses derived from the same public key. Using this technique we were able to merge 2,040,417 clusters, reducing the overall number of clusters from 618,812,655 to 616,772,238.

4.4 A Cross-Chain Clustering Method for Account-Based Systems

By relying only on actively reused keys, the derived addresses in cryptocurrencies with different designs can be associated with a common entity controlling the respective private key. A new non-heuristic based clustering method is to use a retrieved public key in *UTXO based* cryptocurrency *A* to derive potential addresses in *account based* cryptocurrency *B*, thereby associating those addresses to the same entity across different system designs. This also works if addresses (and their associated keys) in cryptocurrency *B* have not yet been actively used in *B*, but the same underlying key has been actively used in *A*.

Building on this basic method, any heuristic based clustering in cryptocurrency *A* can be used to also cluster addresses in another cryptocurrency *B*, for which no clustering is readily available yet, e.g., because *B* is account based while *A* is UTXO based and thus enable applying the multiple-input heuristic. Any available clustering in *A* can be transferred to *B* by computing all derivable addresses (applicable to currency *B*) from obtained public keys within a single cluster in *A* and assign them to a new cluster in *B*, if the respective addresses already exist there. Thereby, multiple-input heuristic clustering from UTXO based cryptocurrencies can be used to cluster account based cryptocurrencies. Figure 5 shows an illustration using Ethereum and Bitcoin as example. Using our techniques we were able to cluster 497,289 Ethereum addresses into 62,681 clusters, and 305,019 Tron addresses into 19,242 clusters, respectively.

Fig. 5. Example of clustering an account-based cryptocurrency such as Ethereum, based on multiple-input clustering in Bitcoin.

4.5 Entities performing Key Reuse

To determine whether key reuse is more prevalent among services and companies or individual end-users, we analyzed attribution data associated with addresses of reused public keys. If these addresses are predominantly linked to known services, it would suggest that services are responsible for the majority of key reuse incidents. Conversely, a lack of such service-specific tags would indicate that end-users are the primary contributors. This approach allows us to empirically analyze the distribution of responsibility for this phenomenon. By merging the addresses exhibiting public key reuse with attribution data from Iknaio²⁰, which builds on the open-source analytics platform GraphSense [Has+21], we identified some entities responsible for key reuse.

A key finding of this analysis is the direct attribution of 1,200 addresses (originating from 894 unique instances of key reuse) to two prominent cryptocurrency exchanges. According to CoinMarketCap²¹ rankings, both entities are among the Top 10 spot exchanges by volume. Specifically, these entities accounted for 792 and 102 reused public keys, respectively. This linkage indicates the contribution of major services to the observed instances of key reuse. While pairwise overlaps are common, we also observe higher-order key intersections involving three or more distinct blockchains (ca. 26%) in these exchange-linked instances. This distribution suggests a systemic reliance on multi-currency key reuse within the operational frameworks of some top-tier spot exchanges.

By cross-referencing public key data with address labels sourced from Dune Analytics²² and Iknaio, we also identified significant key reuse across several other functional categories. Specifically, our analysis revealed 1,297 reused keys associated with *Name Services*, followed by *Contract Deployers* (1,070), *DeFi Bridges* (911), and *Mixing services* (203)²³.

To further understand the network characteristics of key reuse, we constructed a network where nodes represent addresses and undirected edges represent aggregated transactions (incoming or outgoing). As a measure of centrality, we then computed the degree for each address, representing the total number of neighbors with which this address has interacted. Figure 6 illustrates the degree distribution for four cryptocurrencies under consideration. We also mark degrees of nodes with addresses that correspond to attribution data for known exchanges with a small tick above the x -axis. An interesting finding in this regard is the presence of these attributed exchange addresses also across the lower degree spectrum, indicating the use of per-customer addresses, which might then get aggregated. Addresses with a high degree, represented by points in the lower-right (above degree 1,000) of the figure, are potentially associated with services or traders which manage a large volume of transactions. This, as well as the attribution of

²⁰ <https://www.iknaio.com>

²¹ <https://coinmarketcap.com>

²² <https://dune.com>

²³ We conduct a manual investigation of the key reuses in mixing services in [Stü+26, Appendix I].

certain addresses to exchanges, indicates that key reuse is not just happening in private, but also professional contexts.

Fig. 6. Degree (x -axis) distribution in address networks for addresses corresponding to reused public keys. The y -axis is the count of nodes having the respective degree. The ticks above the x -axis correspond to the degrees of specific addresses that have been identified as belonging to exchanges.

5 Discussion and Future Work

For the analyzed cryptocurrencies we dismiss several explanations as the main cause for the observed cross-chain key reuse. An intuitive reason could be the existence of a prior hard-fork or other forking event that led to a permanent chain split [Zam+18; Kal+20]. However, none of the cryptocurrencies herein considered share such a common transaction history with each other.

While we identified 279 weak cryptographic private keys (i.e., private key is a low number $< 2^{32}$ or a 256 bit string of hamming weight < 5) in the set of reused keys, the fact that a significant portion continue to hold value as of today (e.g., 88% of ETH keys hold value and collectively control more than 1 million Ether in total) renders an explanation involving weakly generated cryptographic keys highly unlikely.

Cross-chain *airdrops* could, in principle, offer another explanation but we are not aware of any major events that would help explain the observed scale of key reuse. In HSI the airdrop was performed on the CLAMS network, which is not part of our analysis. For Tron, we considered a major airdrop and token migration when the project launched its own independent Blockchain, however it appears that the addresses associated with the ERC20 token on Ethereum were not automatically reused. Further, unlike most EVM-based chains Tron is not directly compatible with MetaMask and defines its own SLIP44 `coin_type`²⁴, leading to a different key derivation path.

Neither of the previous examples can readily offer an explanation why key reuse also occurs across UTXO and account-based designs, which is the main focus of our analysis. Cross-chain transfer technologies [Zam+21; Aug+24] may yield a plausible answer, in particular since prior work has outlined that address reuse in bridges between EVM-compatible designs appears to be a common occurrence [Lin+25; Yan+25]. However, this observation is only made for cross-chain transfers in account-based cryptocurrencies with *exactly the same* address

²⁴ <https://github.com/bitcoin/bips/blob/master/bip-0044.mediawiki>

format. Specifically, for EVM-compatible designs the associated wallet software often actively encourages key reuse, as we will discuss in the following section.

We are not aware of any technical requirement for cross-chain transfer mechanisms or bridge designs between UTXO and account-based models that necessitate reusing the same secp256k1 keys in both systems. However, it does appear that there exist bridge designs which intentionally perform key reuse between UTXO and account models to improve usability, namely the trusted execution based Avalanche Bridge²⁵. Note that while this bridge primarily operates in the Avalanche cryptocurrency, which we do not consider in this paper, there exists an observable form of *spill-over* in cases where further key reuse occurs between Avalanche and Ethereum. Although we were able to attribute *DeFi Bridges* as one of the functional categories associated with reused keys (see Section 4.5), our results do not suggest that they are responsible for the bulk of the significant number of identified reuse events between UTXO and account based models.

Similarly, while our analysis regarding the entities performing key reuse has revealed that large exchanges are also among those entities, the underlying question why keys are reused between UTXO and account based systems cannot conclusively be answered yet.

Deterministic Key Derivation as the Culprit? Deterministic key derivation is a plausible partial explanation for cross-chain key reuse. While BIP44 aims to provide domain separation via per-cryptocurrency *coin_type* derivation paths, adherence is not guaranteed. Popular wallets such as MetaMask²⁶ and Exodus²⁷ *actively encourage key reuse* by using a single derivation branch across different networks, reducing both privacy and security and explaining address reuse observed in EVM-compatible designs [Lin+25; YHT25]. Whether HD wallet reuse also explains the UTXO–account-based cases remains difficult to verify reliably²⁸ and we leave a detailed investigation to future work.

5.1 Implications

Our observation of significant and active key reuse across different cryptocurrencies and system designs has several implications. Cross-chain key reuse occurs even across fundamentally different system designs (UTXO and account-based), yet our analysis cannot conclusively determine whether this practice is intentional or inadvertent; this highlights the need to better understand its causes and to raise awareness that such reuse can weaken both security and privacy. From a privacy and forensic viewpoint, key-based cross-chain attribution provides ground-truth entity links that do not rely on heuristic clustering rules and can thus be used both to evaluate existing heuristics and to extend UTXO-style clustering techniques into account-based systems. In our entity analysis we also attribute 203 reused

²⁵ A detailed discussion can be found in [Stü+26, Appendix I].

²⁶ <https://metamask.io>

²⁷ <https://www.exodus.com/support/en/articles/8598933>

²⁸ We discuss a possible weak indicator in [Stü+26, Appendix H].

public keys to mixing services. Such behavior creates cross-chain identifiers that may enable deanonymization and can complement existing clustering and tracing approaches, even in contexts explicitly designed to obfuscate transaction flows.

The primary countermeasures are *domain separation* in HD wallet derivation (distinct *coin_types* per cryptocurrency) and per-transaction keys, the latter recommended as best practice since Bitcoin’s inception²⁹ and also preventing replay attacks across forks³⁰ and ECDSA nonce reuse [BH19].

5.2 Limitations

- For UTXO based multi-signature transactions, we did not attempt to identify the actively used public keys for signatures in a t out of n multi-signature transaction. Therefore, we did not consider any public keys retrieved from P2MS and P2SH multi-signature transactions as *actively* used.
- For Zcash, we restricted the analysis to the transparent pool (t-pool), which is comparable to Bitcoin regarding its functionality. The shielded pool (which utilizes zk-SNARKs) does not provide the required transaction details.
- We limited our analysis of Bitcoin and Litecoin to transactions types using legacy as well as SegWit protocols. We did not consider transactions that utilize more recent protocol upgrades, specifically Taproot [JP23], for both Bitcoin and Litecoin, and the *Mimblewimble Extension Blocks* (MWEB) on Litecoin. This decision was made to ensure data set consistency and to avoid complexities introduced by the newer, non-standard transaction formats
- We limited our analysis of account based systems to EOAs, leaving the analysis of smart contract input data to future work.

6 Conclusion

We show that more than 1.4 million secp256k1 keys have *actively* been reused within and across cryptocurrencies, and that this is not a phenomenon of the past. Our measurements characterize key reuse both within individual cryptocurrencies and across fundamentally different designs and reveal that a wide range of entities such as exchanges, bridges, and mixers reuse keys. By relying directly on public keys we provide ground-truth relationships that span multiple systems and are independent of heuristic clustering rules. Further, we demonstrate that key reuse enables the application of clustering techniques that may only be available in certain designs to otherwise incompatible systems, thereby improving the systematic identification of cross-chain entity behavior.

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²⁹ <https://bitcoin.org/bitcoin.pdf>

³⁰ <https://eips.ethereum.org/EIPS/eip-155>

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